

A GSM Technology-based Advanced Invisible Security System Using Infrared Laser Pointer

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ABSTRACT: This paper is all about an invisible security system. In this project we are creating an invisible boundary using infrared laser pointer over the area which we want to protect. Here, few units are present in the system. Boundary breaks in the detection unit, latch circuit unit and sending information unit. When anybody wants to enter in the invisible boundary line, the laser path got interrupted by him, the GSM module will call and send the message on authorized numbers. The system is cost-effective as well as high performing, the main advantage of this system is getting information on breaking the boundary anywhere over the world, and there is no need for the presence of human being near the boundary line.

KEYWORDS: Invisible Security System, Laser, LDR, GSM Technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microstrip Nowadays security is the most prominent part of our life. Crime groups are increasing day by day, they are improving their crime technologies also. So we decided to make an invisible security system to protect the areas, buildings, malls, military fields, etc. The infrared laser pointer is an inexpensive device and its specialty is that, it is only visible at source and incidents points. It goes through long distances without any diffraction. These properties of laser help us to create invisible boundaries for security purposes [1-2]. GSM technology also helps us to make calls and messages to authorized person anywhere in the world, on breaking the security boundary. Ringing buzzer also helps us to make it effective [5, 7]. Fig-1 shows the overall image of the invisible security system.

Fig 1- Overview image of This System

II. MAJOR DEVICES USED IN THE DESIGNING OF INVISIBLE SECURITY SYSTEM

In this paper, there are two electronics devices mainly used for the implementation of this invisible security system. These are a GSM module and a Laser. The implementation of this system can be done easily with a little dedication and small effort by the manufacturer. A brief explanation of these two devices has given below in a section-wise manner.

1.1 GSM MODULE

The GSM/GPRS interface supports the communication between CPU and external devices the board can be used to send and receive SMS as well as to make and receive calls. The board has SIM connectors, which are used to connect with the module and give access to the network. The GSM board has the number of facilities for communicating with the computer, CPU board or other GSM phones. The board can communicate with the CPU board through the six-pin header. The HiLomodule provides UART serial communication, which is available on digital pins 26(Rx) and 13(Tx). These signals are converted to TTL level and can communicate with the PC through DB9 port [5, 7, 9]. Fig-3 describes clearly about a GSM module.

Fig 3- GSM Module

2.2 LASER

Lasers are superb light beams that are powerful enough to zoom miles into the sky or cut to lumps of metal. The fundamental plan of this optical device is very simple. It is a tube that concentrates light over and over again until it emerges in an extremely powerful beam.

A single packet of light is named as a photon. When a photon of a definite colour passes and excited atom it causes that atom to unleash a photon of identical colour and therefore the total light becomes slightly brighter and also the photon of identical colour keeps moving through the material [6]. As it does so, it passes different excited atoms. These also emit photons of the identical colour. As a result a light is amplified/ brightened, making a bright laser beam of the single colour [8]. Fig-2 contains the image of Infrared Laser Pointer.

Fig 2- Infrared Laser Pointer

III. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM & WORKING

Fig 4- Circuit Diagram of Invisible Security System with Laser and GSM Technology

Explanation- In this above circuit (Fig-4), the boundary breaking detection unit is containing three mirrors inclined at 45 degrees so that boundary would be creative properly by infrared laser beam, over the area which we want to protect. The mirrors are adjusted as that if anybody will cross the boundaries the laser beam will get interrupted then the resistance of LDR will be increase. Now due to high resistance the LED will be in reverse biased, so the current will flow from the base of transistor BC548 means it will be in on condition. Since the transistor is on, the relay will trip. Here in the latch circuit we have connected a buzzer and a GSM module with programmed Arduino. On tripping the relay the buzzer will ring and GSM will call and message on authorized numbersimultaneously [4, 7]. Hence the circuitry of this system not so complex and it is easy to maintain.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the end, we made a cost-effective high-performance laser security system. Homes, offices, shopping malls or army areas all have the first priority of its security. So, there is none of the requirement to always see the entrance or boundary line. If any person crosses the boundary (although he has no idea about boundary) the incident line will be interrupted and LDR’s resistance will increase so the transistor will be in on condition, automatically relay will trip and the alarm will ring. Simultaneously due to trip in relay the GSM module with programmed Arduino will call and message on authorised number. It is so much advantageous because we can find information about crossing boundaries anywhere all over the world without any delay [3].

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